

Awareness of Rural Women about JSY Scheme: A Study of State Punjab

Amandeep Kaur Aulakh Sekhon

Department of Sociology, Bahra College of Law, Patiala, Punjab

The objectives of this study were to assess adherence the facilities provided to beneficiaries under JSY Scheme and the awareness about this scheme in rural women in Punjab state, India. For the present study, two districts, the district Patiala and the district Sangrur have been selected from the state of Punjab, on the basis of high-focusing and non-high-focusing districts. Thirteen Community Health Centres have been selected from two Districts. A total one hundred thirty (pregnant women) respondents has selected for the purpose of study. Primary data has been collected with the help of interview schedule. The seven blocks of district Sangrur and six blocks of district Patiala were visited to conduct interview, focused group discussion and observation. Interview schedule prepared to get the views of ASHA workers regarding National Health Mission. Data collected through interview schedule has supplemented through observation. In order to have a deep insight into the feedback of respondents towards the scheme, it becomes necessary to deal with the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents.

Keywords: Janani suraksha yojana, pregnant women, health status, institutional delivery

The National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) seeks to provide equitable and affordable quality healthcare services to rural women and children across the country. Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY) is a safe motherhood intervention scheme under the NRHM. It was launched on 12th April 2005, by the Honourable Prime Minister, Dr. Manmohan Singh and is being implemented in all states and Union Territories with special focus on low performing states. The main objective of the scheme is to reduce maternal and neo-natal mortality by promoting institutional delivery. It is a conditional transfer scheme to promote institutional deliveries, which also makes available quality maternal care during pregnancy, delivery and in the immediate post-delivery period, along with appropriate referral and transport assistance. It is a 100 percent centrally sponsored scheme and links cash assistance with delivery and post-delivery care. Since institutional delivery envisages the use of transport and escort to reach the healthcare institution, the scheme has included transport cost for the pregnant women and payment to ASHA workers for motivating women to opt for institutional delivery. It has also improved accessibility to institutions by building public-private partnerships and providing accreditation to willing private hospitals and nursing homes for delivery services. Under the guidelines of JSY, all the pregnant women from BPL households, SC women, ST women, aged nineteen years and above, delivering in government health centres like sub-centres, PHCs, CHCs, FRUs and general wards of district and state hospitals and also in - accredited private institutions (Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, 2012).

This study attempts to assess the impact of the NHM on the health

Author Note

Dr. Amandeep Kaur Aulakh Sekhon, Assistant Professor
Department of Sociology, Bahra College of Law, Patiala, Punjab
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Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to
Dr. Amandeep Kaur Aulakh Sekhon, Assistant Professor
Department of Sociology, Bahra College of Law, Patiala, Punjab
E-mail: amanaulakh3342@gmail.com

of pregnant women and new born children. Although hospital deliveries have increased considerably since the launch of NRHM and PostNatal Mortality Rate (PNMR) also has been significant decline. NRHM strategy of increasing institutional delivery rate should look into quality of care issues at the time of greatest risk, i.e., birth and the first few days of life, which could be the way forward for reducing the high perinatal death rate in India. However, progress in reducing deaths in perinatal period also depends on other factors like cultural, social and demographic characteristics. These factors also need to be addressed so as to have better social impact on perinatal health. Pregnant women delivered her baby in public health institutions absolutely free and no expense delivery her baby and including caesarean section. The entitlements include free drugs and consumables, free diet up to three days during normal delivery and up to seven days for C-section, free diagnostics, and free blood wherever required. This initiative also provides for free transport facilities from home to institutions, between facilities in case of a referral and drop back home. Similar entitlements were put in place for all sick new-borns accessing public health institutions for treatment till thirty days after birth.

Objectives of the Study

The present study was designed to investigate the participation of women in the activities of JSY Scheme. The objectives of the present study were to assess the impact of the JSY Scheme on women and children's health status. The main objectives of the study were:-

- To assess the social impact of Health care facilities under JSY Scheme on women and children's health.
- To assess the level of knowledge regarding benefits provided under JSY.
- To analyse the stage of pregnancy at which women got registered under JSY.
- To examine the awareness of pregnancy-related complications among respondents.
- To analyse the factors influencing the choice of institutional delivery among beneficiaries.

Hypotheses of the Study

- Rural women will have low level of awareness about JSY.
- Janani Suraksha Yojana has a significant positive impact on promoting institutional delivery and improving maternal healthcare awareness among women.
- Women who receive information from ASHA workers have higher awareness compared to other sources.
- There is a significant relationship between timing of awareness and stage of registration under JSY.
- Women with better knowledge of JSY benefits are more likely to opt for institutional delivery.

Method

The present study was conducted with the aim to examine the participation of rural women in JSY Scheme and the impact of JSY scheme on poor women and child health. The methodology adopted for the study is described below.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in Punjab state. The districts of Punjab had been divided into two parts high- focusing and non-high-focusing by Government of India. The Government of India classifies six districts of Punjab as high focusing districts, which are Gurdaspur, Pathankot, Mansa, Sangrur, Sri Muktsar Sahib and Barnala, because these districts have weak public health infrastructure indicators. For the present study, two districts, i.e., Sangrur and Patiala were selected from Punjab on the basis of high focusing districts and non-high focusing districts respectively. 13 Community Health Centres (CHCs) were selected from two districts Sangrur and Patiala. Moreover ten pregnant women were selected randomly from their registration record. The blocks were selected in such a way so as to make the sample representative of the population.

Pregnant Women who Were Selected for the Study

Districts	CHC Block	Selected Pregnant Women	Total Respondents
Sangrur	7	70	70
Patiala	6	60	60
Total	13	130	130

Note. (Civil Surgeon Office Sangrur and Patiala)

Selection of the Respondents

Out of total number of pregnant women, who were taking benefit under JSY scheme, 10 pregnant women were selected from each CHC block by random sampling. A total of 130 pregnant women were selected for the study.

Measure

The Interview schedule was used for data collection. Interview schedule was pretested. Based on the pre-testing, suitable modifications were made and the interview schedule was finalised. Detailed personal interviews were held with respondents at CHC block and at their residence. Apart from interview, observations were also made during the interview and also when respondents were receiving health facilities at the health centre.

Data Collection

Data was collected personally by the researcher from pregnant

women. Before the actual interview of the respondents, they were assured that the information being collected was required exclusively for research purpose and their personal identity would not be revealed. All the responses from one respondent were obtained at a time. Primary data was collected with the help of interview schedule. This was prepared to get the views of women beneficiaries' regarding JSY scheme. Data collected through interview schedule was supplemented through observation. Secondary data was obtained from Rural Development Department of Government of Punjab, Statistical Abstracts and reports related to JSY Scheme at block, district and State level.

Tabulation and Interpretation of Data

First of all, the relevant information received from the interview schedules was coded. After giving code numbers to qualitative data, tables were prepared. The data was subjected to simple tabulation; cross-tabulation and percentages were calculated to analyze the data. While interpreting the data, attempt was made to incorporate the field observations made during data collection.

Source of Information About JSY

The respondents were asked about the source of information regarding JSY and the responses in this context are given in Table 1.

Table 1

Distribution of the Respondent's on the basis of their Source of Information about JSY

Districts	Source of information about JSY				Total
	ASHA workers	Relatives	AWWs	ANMs	
Sangrur	45 (64.29)	15 (21.42)	07 (10.00)	03 (4.29)	70 (100.00)
Patiala	38 (63.33)	12 (20.00)	08 (13.33)	02 (3.33)	60 (100.00)
Total	83 (63.85)	27 (20.77)	15 (11.54)	05 (3.85)	100 (100.00)

Data in Table 1 show that majority of the respondents, i.e., 63.85 percent came to know about the JSY from AHSA workers, 20.77 percent of the respondents came to know about JSY from relatives, 11.45 percent respondents came to know from AWWs and only 3.84 percent got information from ANMs. Thus, the result shows that ASHA workers emerged as the major source of providing information in majority of the cases.

This highlights the pivotal role of ASHA workers as frontline health functionaries in disseminating maternal health-related information at the grassroots level. Their regular interaction with rural women, home visits, and community-based approach enhance their effectiveness in spreading awareness. Additionally, informal social networks also play a significant role in the diffusion of information. The influence of family members and peers underscores the importance of interpersonal communication in rural settings, where trust and familiarity strongly shape awareness and decision-making processes.

Overall, the study indicates that community-based health workers, especially ASHA workers, play a dominant and effective role in disseminating information, whereas the contribution of other health functionaries remains comparatively limited.

When the Respondents Came to Know About JSY

The respondents were asked when they came to know about JSY and the responses in this context are given in Table 2

Table 2

Distribution of the Respondents on the basis of when they came to know about JSY

Districts	When the respondents came to know about JSY		Total
	Before Pregnancy	During Pregnancy	
Sangrur	12 (17.14)	58 (82.86)	70 (100.00)
Patiala	15 (25.00)	45 (75.00)	60 (100.00)
Total	27 (20.77)	103 (79.23)	100 (100.00)

The data reveals in Table 2 that majority of the respondents, i.e., 79.23 percent respondents came to know about the benefits of JSY during pregnancy and only 20.77 percent of the respondents came to know about it before pregnancy. Thus, the results shows that majority of the respondents came to know about the benefits of JSY during pregnancy.

The findings suggest that awareness about JSY is predominantly generated during pregnancy rather than before it. This indicates a gap in pre-pregnancy awareness, as most women come to know

about the scheme only after they are already pregnant. This pattern highlights the reactive nature of information dissemination, where health interventions are more focused on pregnant women rather than targeting women in the reproductive age group beforehand. Early awareness is crucial, as it enables women to make informed decisions regarding maternal healthcare, institutional delivery, and utilization of scheme benefits in a timely manner. The results further imply that the outreach activities of health workers are largely concentrated on pregnant women, thereby limiting the scope of preventive and preparatory awareness. Strengthening pre-pregnancy awareness campaigns could significantly enhance the effectiveness of the scheme and improve maternal health outcomes. This underscores the need to enhance early awareness initiatives to ensure better utilization of the scheme and improved maternal health planning.

Knowledge about the Benefits of JSY

The respondents were asked whether they had knowledge about the benefits of JSY and the responses in this context are given in Table 3.

Table 3

Distribution of the Respondents on the basis of their Knowledge about the Benefits of JSY

Districts	Knowledge about the benefits of JSY								Total
	ASHA workers provide adequate facilities to the beneficiaries		Amount is credited in their account for the purpose of transportation to pregnant women		Amount is credited in the account of mothers for deliveries in Government Institutions		Post natal services are provided to them		
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	
Sangrur	70 (100.00)	0	32 (45.71)	38 (54.29)	70 (100.00)	0	45 (64.29)	25 (35.71)	70 (100.00)
Patiala	60 (100.00)	0	25 (41.67)	35 (58.33)	60 (100.00)	0	48 (80.00)	12 (20.00)	60 (100.00)
Total	130 (100.00)	0	57 (43.85)	73 (56.15)	130 (100.00)	0	93 (71.54)	37 (28.46)	100 (100.00)

The primary objective of this scheme is to take care of child and the mother at the time of delivery. The care is provided under early registration and regular check-up is essential to avail the benefits under JSY, as well as in recognition of at-risk mothers and appropriate interventions, it is also important for monitoring of the activities (Dongre & Kapur, 2013) It was found in table 3 that all the respondents reported that they knew that ASHA workers provide all kinds of health care facilities to them. More than half of the respondents, i.e., 56.15 percent reported being aware the amount credited in their account for transportation at the time of delivery, while 71.54 percent were aware that post-natal services were provided to them by the ASHA worker. AHA workers play a positive role in guiding pregnant women. Thus, the results shows that the majority of the respondents were aware of various aspects of JSY, like provision for escort by ASHA workers and ASHA workers would stay with pregnant women at the hospital during delivery.

The findings indicate a high level of awareness regarding the general role of ASHA workers and institutional delivery benefits under JSY. This may be attributed to the active involvement of ASHA workers in maternal healthcare services, including

counselling, escorting pregnant women to health facilities, and staying with them during delivery. However, awareness regarding specific financial components, particularly transportation assistance, is comparatively low. This suggests a gap in communication or understanding of certain scheme provisions, which may hinder the full utilization of benefits by beneficiaries. The relatively higher awareness of post-natal services (71.54%) reflects a moderate level of outreach but still indicates that a significant proportion of women remain uninformed about essential follow-up care. Overall, the results highlight that while basic awareness about JSY is strong, there is a need to improve knowledge dissemination regarding specific benefits and entitlements to ensure comprehensive utilization of the scheme. This indicates the need for more focused efforts to enhance understanding of all components of JSY for better maternal health outcomes.

Stage of Pregnancy when Women got Registered Under JSY

The respondents were asked about the time when they got registered under JSY and the responses in this context are given in table 4.

Table 4

Distribution of the Respondents According to the Stage of Pregnancy when the Women got Registered under JSY

Districts	Stage of pregnancy when women got registered under JSY			Total
	1st trimester	2nd trimester	3rd trimester	
Sangrur	21 (30.00)	39 (55.71)	10 (14.29)	70 (100.00)
Patiala	13 (21.67)	36 (60.00)	11 (18.33)	60 (100.00)
Total	34 (26.15)	75 (57.70)	21 (16.15)	130 (100.00)

Data in Table 4 reveals that more than half of the respondents, i.e., 57.70 percent, got registered under JSY at the time of 2nd trimester, 26.15 percent of the respondents got registered at the time of the 1st trimester, and 16.15 percent of the respondents got registered at the time of 3rd trimester. Thus, the result shows that more than half of the respondents got registered under JSY during the time of 2nd trimester.

The findings reveal that a majority of women tend to register under JSY during the second trimester, rather than at the early stage of pregnancy. This indicates a delay in early registration, which is crucial for ensuring timely access to maternal healthcare services such as antenatal check-ups, risk identification, and nutritional support. Although a notable proportion (26.15%) of respondents registered during the first trimester, which is considered desirable, the percentage remains relatively low. Early registration is essential for maximizing the benefits of JSY, as it enables continuous monitoring and early detection of potential complications.

Furthermore, the proportion of women registering during the third trimester (16.15%) highlights existing gaps in awareness and accessibility, as late registration may reduce the effectiveness of healthcare interventions. Overall, these findings suggest that while awareness about JSY is present, timely registration continues to be a challenge. This underscores the need to strengthen the role of health workers, particularly ASHA workers, in motivating and guiding women to register early during pregnancy.

Registration for JSY

The respondents were asked by whom they got registered under JSY and the responses in this context are given in Table 5.

Table 5

Distribution of the Respondents on the basis of their Registration under JSY done by whom

Districts	Registration for JSY				Total
	ASHA workers	AWWs	ANMs	Doctors	
Sangrur	51 (72.86)	11 (15.71)	05 (7.14)	03 (4.29)	70 (100.00)
Patiala	38 (63.33)	13 (21.67)	07 (11.67)	02 (3.33)	60 (100.00)
Total	89 (68.46)	24 (18.46)	12 (9.23)	5 (3.85)	130 (100.00)

Table 5 shows that majority of the respondents, i.e., 68.46 percent got registered under JSY by ASHA workers, 18.46 percent of the respondents got registered by AWWs, 9.23 percent of the respondents were registered under JSY by ANMs and only 3.85 percent of the respondents got registered under JSY by doctors. Thus, the result shows that majority of the respondents got registered under JSY by ASHA workers.

The findings clearly highlight the dominant role of ASHA workers

in facilitating registration under JSY. Their strong presence at the community level, regular interaction with pregnant women, and active involvement in maternal healthcare services make them the primary agents for ensuring enrolment in the scheme. The comparatively lower role of AWWs (18.46%) suggests that although they contribute to the process, their involvement remains secondary to that of ASHA workers. Similarly, ANMs and doctors play a limited role in registration, possibly due to their more institutional and clinical responsibilities, which restrict their direct engagement in community-level mobilization.

These results reflect the effectiveness of community-based outreach mechanisms, where ASHA workers act as a vital link between the healthcare system and rural women. However, the limited involvement of other health functionaries indicates the need for a more integrated approach, wherein all stakeholders actively participate in the registration process to improve coverage and accessibility. These findings are supported by the study of George (2010) which emphasized that ASHA workers significantly influence maternal healthcare utilization through effective counseling, regular home visits, and continuous support, particularly in rural and underserved areas.

Awareness about Complication during Pregnancy

The respondents were asked about the awareness of the complication during pregnancy and the responses in this context are given in Table 6.

Table 6

Distribution of the Respondents based on the Awareness about Complication during Pregnancy

Districts	Awareness about complication during pregnancy		Total
	Yes	No	
Sangrur	45 (64.29)	25 (35.71)	70 (100.00)
Patiala	38 (63.33)	22 (36.67)	60 (100.00)
Total	83 (63.85)	47 (36.15)	130 (100.00)

Table 6 show that more than half of the respondents, i.e., 63.85 percent were aware of the complication during pregnancy and the remaining 36.15 percent of the respondents were not aware of the complication during pregnancy. Thus, the result shows that the majority of the respondents were aware of the complication during pregnancy.

The findings indicate that while a majority of women are aware of complications during pregnancy, a significant proportion still lacks essential knowledge, which may pose risks to maternal health. Awareness of pregnancy-related complications is crucial for timely healthcare-seeking behaviour, early diagnosis, and prevention of adverse outcomes.

The relatively high level of awareness (63.85%) may be attributed to the efforts of community health workers, particularly ASHA workers, who play an important role in educating women through counselling, home visits, and regular interaction.

However, the fact that more than one-third of respondents remain unaware highlights a gap in health education and outreach activities. This lack of awareness may lead to delays in recognizing danger signs and seeking appropriate medical care, thereby increasing the risk of maternal and neonatal complications.

These findings suggest the need for strengthening awareness

programs, especially targeting women in rural and underserved areas, to ensure that all pregnant women are adequately informed about potential complications and the importance of timely medical intervention. A study by Kulkarni (2014) revealed that although awareness levels have improved over time, a considerable proportion of women, particularly in rural areas, still lack adequate

knowledge about pregnancy-related complications, which affects timely healthcare utilization.

Factors Responsible for Opting Institutional Delivery

The respondents were asked about the factors for opting institutional delivery and the responses in this context are given in Table 7.

Table 7

Distribution of the Respondents on the basis of the Factors for Opting Institutional Delivery

Districts	Factors for opting institutional delivery										Total
	Money available under JSY		Better access to institutional delivery		Better care for mother and child		Support provided by AHTSA workers		Previous child was born in an institution		
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	
Sangrur	45 (64.29)	25 (35.71)	32 (45.71)	38 (54.29)	70 (100.00)	0	70 (100.00)	0	48 (68.57)	22 (31.43)	70 (100.00)
Patiala	32 (53.33)	28 (46.67)	39 (65.00)	21 (35.00)	60 (100.00)	0	60 (100.00)	0	31 (51.67)	29 (48.33)	60 (100.00)
Total	77 (59.23)	53 (40.77)	71 (54.62)	59 (45.38)	130 (100.00)	0	130 (100.00)	0	79 (60.77)	51 (39.23)	130 (100.00)

Table 7 show that more than half of the respondents, i.e., 59.23 percent reported that they had opted for institutional deliveries because money was available under JSY and 54.62 percent of the respondents reported that they opted because they got better access there. All the respondents reported that they had opted for institutional delivery for the safety of mother and child, as well as the support they got from ASHA workers during delivery. However, 60.77 percent of the respondents reported that they had opted for the institutional delivery because their previous child was born in an institution and so they had a good experience with the past pregnancy. Thus, the result shows that the majority of the respondents were in favour of opting for institutional delivery.

The findings clearly indicate that multiple factors contribute to the preference for institutional delivery, with financial incentives, accessibility, quality care, and prior experience playing significant roles. The provision of monetary benefits under JSY acts as a motivating factor, especially for economically weaker sections, encouraging them to shift from home-based to institutional deliveries. Similarly, better access to healthcare facilities enhances utilization by reducing physical and logistical barriers.

The fact that all respondents emphasized safety and better care for mother and child highlights the growing awareness regarding the importance of skilled birth attendance and medical supervision during delivery. The support of ASHA workers further strengthens this trend, as they provide continuous guidance, motivation, and assistance throughout the delivery process.

Moreover, previous positive experiences with institutional delivery also influence decision-making, indicating the importance of satisfaction with healthcare services in shaping future health behaviours.

Overall, these findings reflect the success of JSY and community health interventions in promoting institutional deliveries. However, continued efforts are needed to further strengthen accessibility, quality of care, and awareness to sustain and enhance this progress. A study by Kaveri Gill (2009) highlighted that schemes like JSY, which provide cash incentives, have been effective in increasing

institutional delivery rates, especially among economically disadvantaged groups.

Conclusion

The National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) seeks to provide equitable and affordable quality healthcare services to rural women and children across the country. Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY) is a safe motherhood intervention scheme under the NRHM. It was launched on 12th April 2005 by the Honourable Prime Minister and is being implemented in all States and Union Territories with special focus on low-performing states. The majority of the respondents, i.e., 63.85 percent came to know about the JSY from AHTSA workers, 20.77 percent of the respondents came to know about JSY from relatives, 11.45 percent of the respondents got information about JSY from AHTSAs and only 3.84 percent got information about JSY from ANMs. The majority of the respondents, i.e., 79.23 percent of the respondents, came to know about the benefits of JSY during pregnancy and 20.77 percent of the respondents came to know about the benefits of JSY before pregnancy. Thus, the results show that the majority of the respondents came to know about the benefits of JSY during pregnancy. The primary objective of this scheme is to take care of the child and the mother at the time of delivery. The care is provided under early registration and regular check-up is essential to avail the benefits under JSY, as well as in recognition of at risk mothers and appropriate interventions, it is also important for monitoring of the activities. All the respondents reported that ASHA workers provide all kinds of health care facilities to them. More than half of the respondent, i.e., 56.15 percent reported that the amount is credited in their account for the purpose of transportation at the time of delivery, 71.53 percent of the respondents were aware that postnatal services were provided to them by the health worker. AHTSA workers play a positive role in guiding pregnant women. Thus, the results show that more than half of the respondents were aware of various aspects of JSY, like provision for escort by ASHA workers and that ASHA workers will be staying, with pregnant women at the hospital during delivery.

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